

THE EFFECT OF SiC PARTICULATE REINFORCEMENT ON THE AGEING BEHAVIOUR OF ALUMINIUM BASED MATRIX ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

Presented here are the results of an investigation aimed at clarifying the reasons for the differences in precipitation behaviour observed in reinforced, and unreinforced aluminium matrix alloys. We discuss, in this context, the relative effects of SiC interfaces and a composites high dislocation density, on heterogeneous precipitation, as well as the effect of the vacancy concentration on the homogeneous nucleation of low temperature transition phases.

INTRODUCTION

The incorporation of a stiff ceramic reinforcing phase can improve both the modulus and strength of aluminium matrix alloys and SiC particulate reinforced composites are both cheap to make and exhibit little anisotropy. However in such discontinuously reinforced composites it remains the matrix which will determine the yield stress, as well as strongly influencing the UTS and toughness. In order to obtain the best balance of mechanical properties it will be necessary to optimise the matrix microstructure and, to be able to do this by engineering the metallurgy, it is important to understand how precipitation reactions may be affected by the presence of the reinforcing phase.

Various studies of age hardening behaviour in MMCs have been carried out (eg.1-5), and it is generally agreed that precipitation kinetics can be accelerated because of the characteristically high dislocation density in the matrix. This owes its origin to the expansion coefficients of the reinforcement and matrix differing by a factor of 10, and leads to the promotion of phases whose nucleation is heterogeneous and dislocation linked, such as S' and θ' . More interestingly, Rack (4) has observed that the ageing response is slowed down in a 6061 matrix at low temperatures, and accelerated at higher ageing temperatures, when this alloy contains reinforcing SiC whiskers. It is thus not just the effects of dislocation content on heterogeneous nucleation which can be important. There have also been reports of SiC interfaces acting as nucleation sites for precipitation, and this can reduce the composite ductility (eg.6-9), but there remains confusion in this context as to the relative importance of a clean interface, and the effect of oxide contaminants at the interface, in promoting interactions.

Here we describe preliminary results of an investigation designed to clarify the reasons for the differences in ageing behaviour of reinforced and unreinforced aluminium alloys as a function of the matrix type. We followed the precipitation behaviour on ageing using hardness tests, DSC techniques and TEM on model binary matrix systems and conventional alloys, but here data from only two model systems will be discussed.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The specimens examined were made by Alcan Intl. Ltd. using a cospray deposition process (10), which ensures very clean interfaces (11) so that we were able to neglect effects due to oxide interaction. The billets were then extruded. Two binary model alloy matrices were used; Al 2.5wt%Li and Al 4.3wt%Cu. The reinforced and unreinforced materials that were to be compared were made from the same

feed stock, and using the same method, ensuring that the compositions would be the same and that the matrices would then only differ in ways due to the effects of the presence of the reinforcing phase.

Specimens were cut from the extruded bar and solution treated at 530°C and then water quenched. Ageing curves were measured using a Vickers hardness testing machine with a 20Kg load so as to sample a large area on the specimen (results were averaged over at least six indents). TEM foils were prepared by grinding discs to a thickness of <25µm, mounting them on copper washers and then Argon ion beam milling at 15° and 5KV. In conditions where the microstructure was expected to be sensitive to ion beam milling specimens were electropolished. Specimens for differential scanning calorimetry were machined out as 6mm diameter discs 1mm thick, after bulk solution treatment. For the "as quenched condition" discs were reheated to 530°C, for 10 minutes, and then quenched in water and, from the water, directly further quenched in liquid nitrogen. The time taken to transfer the specimens from the furnace to the liquid nitrogen bath was less than 6 seconds. The specimens were then kept in liquid nitrogen until they were used. Specimens had to be loaded into the DSC cell at room temperature, but were immediately cooled to -60°C prior to starting a run. A Perkin Elmer DSC analyzer was used with a liquid nitrogen cooling facility.

RESULTS

From the ageing curves in Fig.1 it can be seen that both the Al-Cu and Al-Li composites show a different response to heat treatment than their respective unreinforced control alloys. The Al-Cu matrix composite, when aged above the GPZ solvus, (Fig.1a) reached peak hardness in only 8h by comparison with the 21h needed for the unreinforced control. However, when aged *below* the GPZ solvus (Fig.1b) the situation is reversed with the initial rise in hardness of the unreinforced control alloy being faster than for the composite. The Al-Li matrix composite responded more quickly to ageing treatments and reached peak hardness earlier than the control (Fig.1c). This latter result is surprising considering that the Al-Li binary system is hardened by the formation of the phase δ' (Al₃Li), which is thought to nucleate homogeneously and independently of the density of lattice defects (14). The dislocation density is of course considerably higher in the reinforced alloys than in their controls.

Comparing the DSC scans in Fig.2a for the reinforced and unreinforced Al-Cu alloys it is apparent that the exotherm and endotherm associated with the formation and dissolution of GP zones progressively disappears as the SiC content is increased. The effect showed consistent trends at different heating rates, but only the 10K/min traces are shown. The exotherm caused by the precipitation of θ' also changes, the phase forming at lower temperatures as the SiC content increases, the temperature difference being some 40K for a SiC content of 15% (comparatively there is a much smaller change in the temperature of the θ exotherm). This behaviour indicates that the activation energy for the nucleation of θ' is reduced by the presence of SiC in the matrix, and this is consistent with the effects of the reinforcement on the ageing behaviour as seen through the hardness changes. However it is also clear that the similarly consistent trends of the diminishing GPZ peaks, and reduced ageing response, *below* the GPZ solvus further indicates that the homogeneous nucleation of GP zones is more difficult in the composite than in the control alloy.

On running DSC scans for the Al-Li binary system we were surprised to find both an exothermic and endothermic reaction occurring *before* δ' precipitates. Papazian et.al (12) have in fact observed a similar effect, which they interpreted as the dissolution of a "GPZ like precursor" to δ'. Here we will attribute these low temperature reactions to the formation of some perhaps "special point ordering" state (SRO) from which δ' does not seem to nucleate, in that it appears to have to be 'rerandomised' before δ' can form. We have not yet identified this "SRO" state by TEM, but the important point is that again, as for Al-Cu, a low temperature transitional state has been suppressed. Even on room temperature ageing the "SRO" is less complete in the reinforced material than in the matrix control, as can be seen by the much smaller SRO "dissolution" endotherm in the composite than in the matrix alone (Fig.2c). Note that the "SRO" exotherm has now disappeared. Phenomenologically it seems that the presence of the "SRO" state delays δ' formation and it is the weaker "SRO" state in the composite which allows earlier δ' formation in this material. That the δ' is formed earlier in the composite than in the control is a consistent explanation for the faster age-hardening behaviour in Fig.1c.

Further evidence for the suppression of the low temperature transition phases in Al-Cu can be seen in Fig.3a, where a comparison is made between reinforced and unreinforced Al-Cu alloys aged at 140°C for 4h. The microstructure for both materials consists of GP zones and early θ'' , but the GPZ density in the composite matrix is much less than in the control. θ' was however observed to form earlier in the composite matrix by TEM investigation, as may be seen by comparing the micrographs in Fig.3b. Both the control alloy and the composite were aged at 195°C for 19h and while the unreinforced alloy contains a bimodal precipitate distribution consisting mostly of θ'' with some θ' , the reinforced composite matrix contains almost exclusively θ' precipitates (note that the cube normal diffraction patterns change consistently with the bright field images). In the composite matrix there is a high dislocation density, prior to ageing, and earlier precipitation of θ' is unsurprisingly encouraged. The importance of a homogeneous, dislocation distribution before ageing, in giving rise to an even distribution of dislocation nucleated phases can be seen in Fig.4. This is a micrograph of a dilutely reinforced SiC composite; near the SiC particle the precipitates are mainly θ' , as in Fig.3b(+SiC), where as further away the precipitate distribution becomes bimodal and appears similar to that in Fig.3b(no SiC). It was found that in regions where the particle spacing was greater than about 10 μ m (this is of course highly dependent on the particle size and geometry) the dislocation fields generated around the particles, due to the partial relaxation of the high thermal stresses caused on quenching (13), do not overlap and the precipitate distribution became very inhomogeneous.

On ageing the Al-Cu composite at 190°C equilibrium θ phase particles were found to decorate the SiC interface in a similar manner to the way they form at high angle grain boundaries. In the context of the direct effects of the interface it is interesting that of the transition phases, though θ'' is unsurprisingly unaffected θ' , despite nucleating on dislocations, is not preferentially nucleated at the SiC particles. On extended ageing however, precipitate free zones near the interface have been observed. In similar work we carried out on the Al-Li alloy 8090 the T₂ phase (Al₆Cu(LiMg)₃) was found to form almost continuously on the SiC interface on over-ageing (190°C for 72h Fig.5) and the PFZs that form near the interface as the T₂ phase grows by dissolving the neighbouring δ' precipitates, were found to be the same width as those caused by T₂ forming on high angle grain boundaries. It can thus be inferred that the SiC interface has a similar potential for reducing the surface energy barrier to nucleation of equilibrium phases, as a high angle grain boundary.

DISCUSSION OF PRECIPITATION BEHAVIOUR IN MMCS

We have provided evidence that the formation of low temperature transition phases (such as GPZs) in a composite is more difficult than in the corresponding unreinforced alloy. In MMCs, which have a large difference in the coefficients of expansion of the reinforcing phase and the matrix, large stresses generated at the reinforcement matrix interfaces on cooling give rise to a high dislocation density in the matrix. Both the presence of lattice defects and the way they will move through the matrix during stress relaxation will greatly increase the rate at which the matrix is rid of excess quenched-in vacancies. Non equilibrium levels of quenched-in vacancies are very important in the formation of GPZs and other low temperature transition phases, and it is on this basis that we suggest that the different kinetics observed for the formation of such phases on low temperature ageing in the composites and controls, can be explained. The fascinating point is that while in the composite the nucleation of GP zones (and θ'') is inhibited, that of δ' is encouraged. This is initially surprising considering that all of these phases involve homogeneous nucleation. Of course the formation temperature of δ' is sufficiently high that although there is a low room temperature vacancy concentration in the composite matrix this, in itself, would have negligible effect on δ' precipitation. The low room temperature vacancy content does however inhibit the formation of the "SRO" in Al-Li matrix composites and the presence of the "SRO" state appears to retard the formation of δ' . Thus, the observed more rapid formation of δ' in the composite material can be accounted for.

Our work, parallels the published literature (2,3) in indicating that phases, such as θ' and S', which nucleate heterogeneously on dislocations, will form earlier in the ageing sequence in a composite than in the matrix alone. This is because of the greater density of nucleation sites provided by the higher dislocation density in the composite. However as we have demonstrated, unless the dislocation fields from individual reinforcing particles overlap such phases will not be homogeneously distributed, so that the local matrix microstructure can be expected to be highly variable at low volume fractions, and for inhomogeneous particle distributions.

The high surface energy of SiC interfaces and high angle grain boundaries lowers the energy barrier to the nucleation of phases by reducing the overall surface energy term. Hence the intermetallic precipitates which nucleate on interfaces tend to be the equilibrium phases (rather than for example θ') since they are normally fully incoherent with the matrix. PFZs can also form in association with interface precipitation, with a resultant decrease in hardness as the PFZs grow. Mechanically deformed alloys develop pronounced textures, and the misorientations between grains are often small even on recrystallization. Thus, by incorporating SiC particles into the matrix the precipitation modes normally associated with grain boundary nucleation are much encouraged. In MMCs stress is already concentrated at the reinforcement matrix interface, so any precipitation of brittle intermetallic phases at the interface would be expected to have a marked effect on the composite fracture characteristics (as has been reported 8,9).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Vacancy associated transition phase formation is kinetically inhibited in aluminium matrix composites.
2. Precipitation reactions which involve nucleation at dislocations are accelerated in a composite.
3. The distribution of dislocation nucleated phases will be homogeneous only if the dislocation fields associated with SiC particles overlap strongly.
4. The precipitation of incoherent phases, with high surface energies, takes place preferentially on SiC interfaces in a similar manner to the way this occurs at high angle grain boundaries, and the reinforcement effectively increases the internal surface area for such precipitation.

In short; the precipitation behaviour in the matrix of a composite can be very different from that in the matrix alone, with both *homogeneous* and *heterogeneous* precipitation reactions being affected, in the former case by inferred changes in the vacancy concentration, and in the latter either by the dislocation content for semicoherent phases or by the change in internal surface area for incoherent phases.

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REFERENCES

1. S. Abis and G. Donzelli; J. Mat. Sci. Let. Vol.7 (1988) pp. 51-52
2. T. G. Nieh and R. F. Karlak; Scripta. Met., Vol.18 (1984) pp. 25-28
3. T. Christman and S. Suresh; Acta. Met., Vol.36, No.7 (1988) pp. 1691-1704
4. H. J. Rack; ICCM6 London July 1987, Ed. F. L. Mathews, pp. 2.382-2.389
5. M. A. Bayoumi, H. Ribes and M. Suery; 9th Risø Int. Symp. Sept. 1988 pp. 291-296
6. S. R. Nutt; "Interfaces in MMCs" Met. Soc. of AIME (1986) pp.157-167
7. S. R. Nutt and R. W. Carpenter; Mat. Sci. and Eng. Vol.75 (1985) pp. 169-177
8. C. Liu, S. Pape and J. J. Lewandowski; ICCI-II June 1988, Ed. H. Ishida, pp. 513-524
9. J. J. Lewandowski, C. Liu and W. H. Hunt Jr.; Symp. P/M Committee of TMS/AIME, Denver, Feb. 1987, Ed. P. Kumar, pp. 117-137
10. J. White, T. C. Willis, I. R. Hughes and R. M. Jordan; TMS/AIME Annual Conf., Phoenix, Jan. 1988, pp. 693-708
11. T. J. Warner, P. J. Withers, J. White, R. M. Jordan, and W. M. Stobbs; ICCI-II June 1988, Ed. H. Ishida, pp. 537-552
12. J. M. Papazian, C. Sigili and J. M. Sanchez; Scripta. Met. Vol. 20 (1986) pp. 201-206
13. M. Taya and T. Mori; Acta. Met., Vol. 35, No.1 (1987) pp. 155-162
14. P. L. Makin; PhD Thesis Sept. 1985, Cambridge

Fig.1 Age hardness curves for reinforced (Al-2.5%Li +10 Vol.% SiC_p and Al-4.3%Cu +14 Vol.% SiC_p) and unreinforced control alloys (no SiC). In 1.a and 1.c the composite matrix reaches peak hardness earlier, however below the GPZ solvus (in 3.b) the unreinforced alloy initially has the higher hardening rate.

Fig.2 DSC Traces over the range -60 to 500°C with a scanning rate of 10K/min. Traces are shifted relative to each other for clarity. Exothermic (precipitation) and endothermic (dissolution) reactions are indicated as ΔH- and ΔH+ respectively. Note the reduction in size of the peaks of the low temperature transition phases, and the shift of the θ' precipitation exotherm (2a) to a lower temperature, with increasing SiC content.

Fig.3 A comparison of unreinforced and composite matrix (Al4.3%Cu alloy) microstructures for two different heat treatments: **3a**, 4h at 140°C (below the GPZ solvus) and **3b**, 19h at 195°C (above the GPZ solvus). In **3a** the unreinforced material can be seen to have a much higher density of GPZs than the reinforced matrix. In **Fig.3b** the composite matrix is almost entirely θ' while the unreinforced alloy has a bimodal distribution of mainly θ'' with some areas of θ' . Micrographs are for near cube orientations, and corresponding cube normal diffraction patterns are shown.

Fig.4 Al-Cu matrix composite (only 8.5 vol.% SiC) aged for 24h at 190°C, and in a low volume fraction region. Close to the SiC particle (**a**) the microstructure consists of θ' while further away, on the edge of the dislocation field (**b**), there is a bimodal distribution of θ'' and θ' .

Fig.5 Super lattice dark field image of δ' in 8090 aged 190°C for 72h. The PFZ formed by the precipitation of the T₂ phase is the same width at the high angle GB and at the SiC interface.